

GEGN Research Fair Abstract

InSAR Analysis of Surface Subsidence above a Headrace Tunnel in the Sri Lankan Highlands

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The Uma Oya Multipurpose Development Project (UOMPDP) is currently under construction in the Badulla district of Sri Lanka. The project, designed to provide power and irrigation water to local residents, consists of two dams, a hydropower station, and two tunnels totaling ~23 km in length. Excavation of the headrace tunnel at depth (>350m) through heavily tectonized and fractured, high-grade metamorphic rock of the Sri Lankan highlands has led to excessive water ingress as a recurring problem during the construction phase of the UOMPDP. The most recent series of inflows initiated in Fall 2016, with peak discharge values reaching $1.3 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ during the Summer of 2017. Since late 2016, over 2,000 wells, streams, and springs have run dry and cracks have been reported on over 4,000 surface structures in areas near the tunnel alignment. In order to identify and measure surface deformation associated with this major drainage event, a dataset of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellite images with high temporal resolution were acquired by Sentinel-1, and were processed to produce Interferometric SAR (InSAR). Thirty-three scenes acquired between July 2016 and January 2018 reveal spatially and temporally dynamic subsidence surrounding the tunnel axis. Localized subsidence is first observed in early 2017, and subsequently expands into a circular shape reaching 5 km in diameter. The expansion of the subsiding area coincides with the period of time in which measured subsidence rates and water ingress rates were at their peak. A maximum total deformation of ~9 cm is measured in the satellite line of sight direction. These results highlight the potential use of InSAR as a monitoring tool for underground excavation in terms of determining the water ingress source extent, and for public safety to quickly identify areas at risk of experiencing rapid subsidence.